

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Qulmatov Qurvonali Zokirali o'g'li

DASTURIY TA'MINOTNI TESTLASH USULLARI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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